

**INDONESIAN BILDUNGSROMAN
IN PRAMOEDYA ANANTA TOER'S THE BURU QUARTET**

DONO SUNARDI

OCTOBER 2011

A THESIS

**Submitted to the faculty of Clark University, Worcester,
Massachusetts, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for
the degree of Master of Arts in the department of English**

And accepted on the recommendation of

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "Step M. Levin". The signature is written in a cursive, flowing style.

Stephen M. Levin, Ph.D., Chief Instructor

of Indonesia. Finding the dynamicity and hybridity in Minke means rediscovering the dynamic and hybrid nature of Indonesian nationalism.

Stephen M. Levin, Ph.D.

Chief Instructor

James Elliot, Ph.D.

Assistant Professor

Paul Ropp, Ph.D.

Professor